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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Left Behind

Life is not meant to be constant.
Some people are meant to go places,
while some are just left behind.
But the hardest part is not about being forsaken,
it is the part wherein you have to learn to walk alone.

Being left behind is not the end,
for it clears the path for you to rise ahead.
It gives you the power to measure your own strength.
It gives you the chance to know who you really are.

The world will continue to move on without you,
BUT SO, CAN YOU!

Sooner or later, you will learn to smile again.
At some point, you will, once again hear the chirping of
the birds and the buzzing of the bees.
Ultimately, you will learn to survive, to persevere.

Being left behind is not always a curse,
it is a chance to live again.